

RESOURCES**ANTI-AMERICANISM: RECENT SOURCES**

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*No one likes us
I don't know why.
We may not be perfect
But heaven knows we try.*

But all around even our old friends put us down

Randy Newman, 'Political Science', from the album *Sail Away* (1972).

Anti-American sentiment has, it would seem, increased in the wake of the election of George Bush, jr. and the US's response to the events of September 11. Commentators within the US, and globally, have analysed the recent variants of a long-standing condition. Below is a review of recent coverage of the phenomenon. The entries for the print sources are divided into:

- (1) analyses of anti-Americanism written in the US,
- (2) accounts of international expressions of anti-Americanism.

1. US SOURCES**Books**

Chua, A. *World on Fire: How Exporting Free Market Democracy Breeds Ethnic Hatred and Global Instability*, Doubleday, New York, 2002.

Chua argues that free market globalisation produces a backlash in countries around the world (including those of Africa, Asia and Latin America) in the form of ethnic conflict and anti-capitalist and anti-American politics.

Hollander, P. *Understanding Anti-Americanism: Its Origins and Impact at Home and Abroad*, Ivan R. Dee Publisher, [New York], 2004.

This book is listed as forthcoming at Amazon.com.

McPherson, A. *Yankee No! Anti-Americanism in US-Latin American Relations*, Harvard University Press, 2003.

Packer, G (ed.). *The Fight is for Democracy: Winning the War of Ideas in America and the World*, Perennial, New York, 2003.

A collection of essays dealing with America's position in the post-September 11 world. The views of Noam Chomsky once again become the

liberals' yardstick of a leftist interpretation of US foreign policy to be avoided or revised.

Rosenfeld, A. *Anti-Americanism and Anti-Semitism: A New Frontier of Bigotry*, American Jewish Committee, New York, 2003.

The author examines the roots, expansion, and meanings of anti-Americanism and anti-Semitism. The focus of the book is the convergence of anti-Americanism and anti-Semitism throughout the Muslim world and in Germany and France.

Rubin, B. and J. Rubin (eds.). *Anti-American Terrorism and the Middle East: A Documentary Reader*, Oxford University Press, New York, 2002.

A collection of documents including Osama bin Laden's 1996 declaration of war against the 'Zionist-crusaders alliance', and 'Why Attack America' by his close associate Aymam al-Zawahiri.

Vidal, G. *Perpetual War for Perpetual Peace: How We Got To Be So Hated*, Thunder's Mouth/Nation Books, New York, 2002.

Vidal's book comprises a collection of musings originally published in *Vanity Fair* magazine, Britain's *Observer* newspaper, and elsewhere. Vidal ranges from reflections on Timothy McVeigh (who wrote to Vidal while in prison) and Osama bin Laden, among others. Todd Gitlin critically reviews Vidal's book in *Dissent*, winter 2003.

Journal essays, newspaper articles, online sources

'Dissent from the Homeland: Essays after September 11', *The South Atlantic Quarterly*, vol. 101, no. 2, spring 2002.

A special issue of the journal, comprising essays which analyse anti-Americanism from a variety of perspectives. Contributors include Stanley Hauerwas, a Protestant theologian, Frank Lettrichia, literary theoretician, Jean Baudrillard (a translation of his piece for *Le Monde* on the essence of terrorism), Rowan Williams, the Archbishop of Canterbury, and Vincent Cornell, professor of Muslim studies at the University of Arkansas. Todd Gitlin's review of this volume in *Dissent*, winter 2003, points to the unevenness of the collected essays (in terms of levels of analysis and political position).

Gitlin, Todd, 'Anti-Anti-Americanism', *Dissent* online, Winter 2003, <http://www.dissentmagazine.org/menutest/articles/wi03/gitlin.htm>

D. Jennings. 'Varieties of Anti-Americanism', *The Washington Dispatch*, August 4, 2003, online at <www.washingtondispatch.com>.

Facile assertions in the form of an Op-Ed piece outlining three types of anti-Americanism: against US capitalism; by the 'world's traditionalists'; and 'all manner of "intellectuals" and leftists' who 'hate American because America has proved that capitalism works.'

Worth, D. and D. Walsh. 'Anti-Americanism: The "Anti-Imperialism" of Fools' at <www.wsws.org>. An essay, dated 22 September, 2001, from the World Socialist Website. The authors sympathize with the victims of September 11 and criticise commentators, such as Charlotte Raven writing in the *Guardian* (UK) on September 18, for failing to differentiate between 'the US' and 'the US government' as the cause and object of anti-Americanism.

Glazov, J. 'Anti-Americanism' at <FrontPageMagazine.com>. Dated November 11, 2002 the posting is a forum on the causes, forms and possible consequences of anti-Americanism. Participants include Paul Hollander, professor emeritus of sociology at the University of Massachusetts; Stanley Kurtz, a research fellow at the Hoover Institution and an editor of *National Review Online*; and others.

Leupp, G. 'Random Thoughts on "Anti-Americanism" and on Good, Evil, Duck Eggs and Warm Beer in China' at <www.counterpunch.org>. The essay, dated September 24, 2002, is posted at the site of *CounterPunch* ('America's Best Political Newsletter' according to its web banner), edited by Alexander Cockburn and Jeffrey St Clair. Drawing on his experiences in China, the author (an associate professor in the History Department of Tufts University) addresses the questions, 'What does it mean to be anti-American, or to adhere to the posited ideology, anti-American?'

Montgomery, D. 'Mexican Anti-Americanism in America', December 6, 2002 at <FrontPageMagazine.com>. The essay details aspects of anti-American sentiment among the US's sizeable Mexican and Mexican American population.

Neumann, M. 'Anti-Americanism: Too Much of a Good Thing?' at <www.counterpunch.org>. Dated September 13, 2003. Neumann, a professor of philosophy at Trent University in Ontario, argues that anti-Americanism will not change US policies. He points to ways to exploit US self-interest and the limitations of US foreign policy as effective responses to wayward US military power.

'Pan-Macedonians to Bush: "You Spread Anti-Americanism"', *The Hellenic News of America* at <www.hellenicnews.com>.

A report of a three-day conference of the Pan-Macedonian Association of America and the contents of a letter written by the Association to the US President in which it was argued that US recognition of a non-existent country called Yugoslavia would help spread anti-Americanism.

‘Brands in an Age of Anti-Americanism’, *Business Week* online. Posted August 4, 2003.

http://www.businessweek.com/magazine/content/03_31/b3844011_mz046.htm

2. INTERNATIONAL SOURCES

Books

Barnes, P. *Le XXI^e Siecle ne sera pas americain*, Editions du Rocher, Paris, 1998 and 2000. Barnes, a French Socialist senator, looks to Britain and especially Germany as nations which, he hopes, will rid themselves of US political dominance.

Collon, M. *Poker menteur*, Editions EPO, Bruxelles, 2000. The author, a Belgian Marxist journalist, links anti-Americanism and anti-Germanism. He argues that both the US and Germany were responsible for the dissolution of Tito’s Yugoslavia; Germany saw the opportunity to extend its control of central Europe, in alliance with the US. This book, together with those listed here by Guillaume, Barnes, Delmas, and Debray are reviewed in M. Schutz, ‘Euro-skepticism and Anti-Americanism Erupt in Europe’, *Culturekiosque* at <www.culturekiosque.com/nouveau/books/europeanunion.html>.

Crockatt, R. *America Embattled: 9/11, Anti-Americanism and the Global Order*, Routledge, London, 2003. The author teaches American Studies at the University of East Anglia. The book examines terrorism in contemporary historical contexts, and the reasons for acts of terrorism against the US.

Debray, R. *Le code et la glauve*, Editions Albin Michel/Foundation Marc Bloch, Paris, 1999. Debray, one-time collaborator of Che Guevara, argues that any alliances between France and Germany to challenge US hegemony in Europe are bound to fail, given the self-defeating self-interest of both countries. Debray is also critical of the European Union which, he argues, is based on a debilitating denial of national differences.

Delmas, P. *De la prochaine guerre avec a’Allemagne*, Editions Odile Jacob, Paris, 1999. The author argues that France, with the assistance of Germany,

should lead European affairs, thereby excluding US political interests in Europe.

Guillaume, F. *Le complot des maitres du pouvoir*, Editions Lattes, Paris, 2000. Guillaume, depute, former Minister, and leader of the agricultural lobby in France, argues that a Washington-led NATO intervention in the Kosovo conflict demonstrated US political and military involvement in Europe and the degree of accommodation with this situation undertaken by most European powers.

Neville, R. *Amerika Psycho: Behind Uncle Sam's Mask of Sanity*, Ocean Press, New York, 2002. A collection of essays on aspects of American society (Hollywood, advertising, the oil industry). The title essay- described by some readers as anti-American, according to Ashley Hay in *The Bulletin* (vol.120, no.39)- was originally published in *The Good Weekend* section of the *Sydney Morning Herald* on May 19, 2001.

Revel, J-F. *L'obsession anti-americaine: son fonctionnement, ses causes, ses consequences*, Plon, Paris, 2002. Revel defends the US in the face of anti-American sentiment and argues that what he calls the 'anti-American obsession' is the result of a deliberate disregard of the central political, social, and economic traditions of the US. Revel's thesis is that much anti-Americanism is a form of anti-capitalism on the part of segments of the global population wedded to illiberal, even totalitarian, doctrines. The book spent several weeks at the top of French bestseller lists in late 2002.

Roger, P. *L'ennemi americain: genealogie de l'antiamericanisme francais*, Seuil, Paris, 2002. A history of both left and right variants of anti-Americanism in France over the past 200 years. (Reviewed in W. Mead, "Why Do They Hate Us? *Foreign Affairs*, March/April 2003).

Sardar, Z. and M. Wyn Davies. *Why Do People Hate America?*, Icon Books, London, 2002. The British authors focus on Washington's economic policies and American culture *in toto* as the root causes of anti-Americanism.

Shiraev, E. and V. Zubok. *Anti-Americanism in Russia: From Stalin to Putin*, Palgrave Macmillan, London, 2000. The role of NATO and European expansionism are topics examined in this account of contemporary anti-Americanism in Russia.

Journal essays, newspaper articles, online sources

'Anti-Americanism in Korea: Closing Perception Gaps' at <http://csis.org.htm>. A five chapter report written by a number of South Korean authors on the 'rising tide of anti-Americanism in South Korea.' The report is mounted on the website of the Center for Strategic and International Studies (CSIS). The CSIS is, according to its online information, an organisation 'dedicated to providing world leaders with strategic insights on- and policy solutions to- current and emerging global issues.' The CSIS is headed by John Hamre, formerly US deputy secretary of defence, and Brent Scowcroft chairs the board of governors of 'Pacific Forum CSIS'.

'The Blind Alley of Crude Anti-Americanism'-www.socialistfuture.org.uk. This recent essay, on the website of the Movement for a Socialist Future (UK), argues, in a level-headed and well-researched way, that movements which criticise or seek to undercut the US economy run the risk of reinforcing local chauvinist positions. The anonymous essay argues, instead, that '[w]e should reject nationalist, anti-Americanism and campaign instead for a new political and economic democracy based on the power of the majority.'

Gimelstein, A. 'The Origins of Russia's Anti-Americanism', *Pravda*, online at <<http://english.pravda.ru>>. Briefly compares and contrasts Russian (and Soviet) and US imperialism and mentions the US role as world gendarme. (The English translation results in a number of interesting turns of phrase, such as 'There is hardly anything nice in the Iraqi regime').

Knox, P. 'The Rise of Anti-Americanism', *The Globe and Mail*, December 4, 2002, p.A25, online at <www.globeandmail.com>. A response to reports in *The Globe and Mail* that Canadians are anti-American. Knox argues that Canadians are aligned with Americans in the need to defeat terrorism.

New Perspectives Quarterly, vol. 20, no. 2, spring 2003. French perspectives on anti-Americanism are presented in this special issue of the journal. The volume includes the essays 'Anti-Americanism in the Old Europe', an interview by Nathan Gardels, the editor of *NPQ*, with prominent French philosopher Bernard-Henri Levy; 'Contradictions of the Anti-American Obsession', an extract from Jean-Francois Revel's *L'obsession anti-americaine: son fonctionnement, ses causes, ses consequences*; and 'The Costs of Lite [sic] Anti-Americanism' by Moises Naim, the editor of the journal *Foreign Policy* (and formerly minister of trade and industry in Venezuela).

Rushdie, S. 'Anti-Americanism Has Taken the World by Storm', the *Guardian*, February 6, 2002, online at <www.guardian.co.uk>.

Rushdie argues that '...America finds itself facing an ideological enemy that may turn out to be harder to defeat than militant Islam: that is to say, anti-Americanism...'

'What We Think of America', *Granta*, issue 77, spring 2002.

A collection of 24 essays which analyse anti-Americanism from various national perspectives, including Canada, Chile, India, and England.

Internet Resources:

There are no web sites *per se* that we can locate dedicated to anti-Americanism. There are however numerous web sites that deal with issues that give or gave rise to anti-Americanism.

The National Security Archive is an independent non-governmental research institute and library located at The George Washington University in Washington, D.C. The Archive collects and publishes declassified documents acquired through the Freedom of Information Act (FOIA) <http://www.gwu.edu/~nsarchiv/>

Cuba: Thirteen Days and History: <http://www.cubanmissilecrisis.org/> contains commentary, memoirs and links to audio on the Cuban missile crisis.

The Philippines American War: <http://www.boondocksnet.com/> includes material on American anti-imperialism.

Vietnam War: Phoenix Program PSYOP Comics:
<http://www.parascope.com/articles/0497/phxcomic.htm>

World War II no-no boys: Excerpt from Eric Muller's book *Free to Die for Their Country: The Story of the Japanese American Draft Resisters in World War II* and useful links to aspects of Japanese American internment. <http://www.press.uchicago.edu/Misc/Chicago/548228.html>

The State Department's attempts to counter anti-Americanism can be found in a series of online journals at <http://usinfo.state.gov/journals/journals.htm>

The Federation of American Scientists often takes issue with the US government's claims about various developments in other countries particularly with regard to weapons: <http://www.fas.org/index.html>

The Propaganda Remix Project

<http://homepage.mac.com/leperous/PhotoAlbum1.html>

Satire reworking American propaganda posters.

Uncle Sam Image Gallery

Not anti-American as such, but Uncle Sam is an enduring symbol of America and as such a frequent whipping boy for Anti-Americans

<http://home.nycap.rr.com/content/unclesam.html>